

Assessing the socio-economic feasibility of green mussel cultivation in Demak, Indonesia

Overview of indicators and survey questions

1. Demographic Distribution

Indicator	Survey question
Name	What is your name?
Gender	What is your gender?
Age group	What is your age?
Education level	What is the highest form of education you received?
Primary occupation	What is the most important profession for your income?
Secondary job(s)	Do you have other job(s) next to your main job? If yes, please explain what type of other job(s) you have.
Awareness and perception of international projects (e.g., MuMaCo)	Are you aware of the MuMaCo project or other international projects? What is your perception of this/these projects? Please explain.

2. Financial & Market Feasibility

Indicator	Survey question
Species harvested	Which species do you harvest?
Portion of harvest for domestic consumption	What portion of your harvest is used for domestic consumption?
Weekly harvest quantity (kg)	What are the approximate harvested quantities in kilograms of fresh (shell)fish in an average WEEK of the year? Please explain.
Weekly income from fisheries/aquaculture (IDR)	How much IDR do you earn PER WEEK with fisheries and/or aquaculture?
Expected minimum income from mussel farming (IDR/week)	Imagine you will engage in green mussel cultivation. What is the lowest income (IDR/WEEK) you expect to earn?
Willingness and ability to invest in mussel farming	Would you be able/willing to invest in green mussel cultivation (e.g. bamboo)? Please explain.
Minimum and maximum investment (IDR)	If you are willing to invest in green mussel cultivation, what is the MINIMUM amount of IDR you would be willing/able to invest? What is the MAXIMUM amount of IDR you would be willing/able to invest?
Maximum hours per week willing to work	What is the maximum amount of hours PER WEEK that you are willing to spend on mussel cultivation?
Ease of selling mussels in local markets	How easy/hard is it to sell mussels on local markets? Please explain why?

Indicator	Survey question
Ease of getting fair prices	How easy/hard will it be for you to get a fair price for mussels? Please explain why.
Lowest acceptable price per kg of mussels (IDR)	What would be the lowest acceptable price in IDR per kg of mussels? Please explain.
Popularity of mussel consumption in the village	What is the degree of popularity of consuming mussels in your village? Please explain why.
Maximum acceptable travel time to production site (hours/day)	Imagine you will engage in green mussel cultivation. What is the maximum travel time (HOURS/DAY) between your house and the production location? Please explain.
Maximum acceptable travel cost (IDR/day)	Imagine you will engage in green mussel cultivation. What are the maximum costs you are willing to pay for travelling in IDR/DAY? Please explain.

3. Main Barriers

Indicator	Survey question
Barriers to switching to mussel farming	Please indicate the 3 MOST IMPORTANT main barriers for you to change your current job to green mussel cultivation. Number 1: most important, number 2: second most important, number 3: third most important.
Impact of coastal flooding and land subsidence	How does coastal flooding and/or land subsidence affect your daily life? Please explain.
Actions taken to reduce flooding and their outcomes	Have you tried to take action to reduce coastal flooding? If yes, please explain which actions. If you answered 'yes': what were the results of your action? Please explain.
Concern about future income loss due to flooding	How worried are you about coastal flooding affecting your income in the future?
Willingness to pay to prevent flooding (IDR/week)	What would you be willing to pay in IDR per WEEK to stop coastal flooding in your area?